

Solute diffusion in single germinating seed – experimental determination of diffusion coefficients of NaCl and CaCl₂·2H₂O in PBW-373 wheat variety at 25° and 45°

M. L. Sood* and Ashima Passi

Department of Biochemistry and Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004, India

E-mail : mlsood28@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 16 October 2001, revised 25 March 2003, accepted 19 June 2003

Both integral and differential diffusion coefficients of NaCl and CaCl₂ in the concentration range varying from 0.03 to 1 M and 0.01–1 M at 25° and 45° were determined in a promising wheat variety viz. PBW-373 by using a diffusion cell of 13 ml capacity and employing a single seed rather than bulk seeds (10 or 5 nos) as used in earlier work. Fingerprinting of the variety was done by determining the seed constant (β_{seed}) whose value determined was 97×10^{-3} and which is different from the values of 137×10^{-3} , 179×10^{-3} , 88.8×10^{-3} and 61.3×10^{-3} obtained for the other four varieties viz. PBW-154, PBW-175, PBW-226 and PBW-343. The work has further supported that diffusion technology, as a tool can be successfully exploited for fingerprinting the seeds. From the results of diffusion coefficients it was also concluded that the seed membrane acts as a sensitive selective barrier that allow specific amount of the solutes at different concentrations to diffuse into it.

A theory of diffusion was earlier developed and diffusion cell apparatus designed and fabricated for determining diffusion coefficients in germinating seed in this laboratory¹. Extensive work was later carried out which included refined methodology and determination of diffusion coefficients of simple valence salts²⁻⁴, extension of the theory to pollen grains⁴ and for studying multicomponent systems⁵. In all the above work, bulk seeds (10 to 5 nos) rather than single were employed and diffusion coefficients in single seed, which is the average value determined²⁻⁴. The present work is an extension of the earlier one in which single seed rather than bulk has now been used and diffusion coefficients of NaCl and CaCl₂ in a promising wheat variety determined at 25° and 45°.

Results and discussion

The value of seed constant (β_{seed}) obtained for the wheat variety PBW-373 viz. 97×10^{-3} is different from those obtained earlier⁶ indicating clearly that the PBW-373 strain of wheat is a new variety, whose membrane characteristics are different from the above wheat varieties. This value of seed constant (97×10^{-3}) is therefore the "fingerprint" value of the PBW-373 wheat variety.

Determination of differential diffusion coefficients (D):

The values of integral diffusion coefficients obtained by the use of eqn. (4) were next converted to a more fundamental differential diffusion coefficients by employing the well known method due to Stokes⁷. According to this the

integral diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}) is related to the differential diffusion coefficient (D) by the equation :

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{C_m' - C_m''} \int_{C_m''}^{C_m'} D.dC \quad (1)$$

Stokes⁷ defined \bar{D} as an integral diffusion coefficient for a diffusion run of very short duration and gives the relation

$$\bar{D}^{\circ} = \frac{1}{C} \int_0^C D.dC \quad (2)$$

The graphical integration procedure for determining diffusion coefficient D for sintered diaphragm cells from the integral value \bar{D} has been discussed earlier^{6,7}. This method was applied in the case of germinating seed since seed coat/membrane is also porous in nature, so the above procedure can be applied for the determination of D from \bar{D} for germination seeds. In the present work using the wheat variety the plots of \bar{D} vs C for aqueous (0.01–1 M) NaCl and CaCl₂·2H₂O at 25° and 45° are shown in Fig. 1. The $\bar{D}_{\text{cm}}^{\circ}$ values obtained were 3.9×10^{-4} , 2.8×10^{-4} , 4.15×10^{-4} and $2.32 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively. The plots of \bar{D}° vs $\sqrt{cm'}$ are shown in Fig. 2. Since the values of $\bar{D}_{\text{cm}}^{\circ}$ were found to be constant further plotting was not considered necessary. From the plots of \bar{D}° data vs \sqrt{C} (which were not linear), the slope at each point was determined by the least square method. D values for both the salts are recorded in

Tables 1 and 2. The plots of D vs \sqrt{C} are shown in Fig. 3.

From the results of diffusion coefficient (D) recorded for NaCl-PBW-373 at 25° and 45° in Table 1, it can be concluded that with the exception at 0.10 and 0.70 M, the differential diffusion coefficient at 25° was found to increase with increase in the electrolytic concentration as compared to the D values at 45°. Similarly for $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -PBW-373 (Table 2) except at 0.01, 0.50 and 1.0 M the D values

Fig. 1. Plots of \bar{D} vs \sqrt{C} : (O) NaCl-PBW-373 at 25°; (Δ) NaCl-PBW-373 at 45°; (\square) CaCl_2 -PBW-373 at 25°; (\bullet) CaCl_2 -PBW-373 at 45°.

Fig. 2. Plots of \bar{D}'_{cm} vs $\sqrt{C_m}$: (O) NaCl-PBW-373 at 25°; (Δ) NaCl-PBW-373 at 45°; (\square) CaCl_2 -PBW-373 at 25°; (\bullet) CaCl_2 -PBW-373 at 45°.

Fig. 3. Plots of D vs \sqrt{C} : (O) NaCl-PBW-373 at 25°; (Δ) NaCl-PBW-373 at 45°; (\square) CaCl_2 -PBW-373 at 25°; (\bullet) CaCl_2 -PBW-373 at 45°.

Table 1. Integral (\bar{D}) and differential (D) diffusion coefficients ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) of NaCl-PBW-373 wheat system at 25° and 45°

Concn. mol dm^{-3}	25°		45°	
	\bar{D}	$D \times 10^4$	\bar{D}	D
0.03	3.2791	3.3662	1.2780	1.5200
0.05	—	—	1.5610	1.6644
0.07	1.5962	1.7715	1.4520	1.6644
0.10	1.1812	1.2205	1.5030	1.6784
0.30	3.9768	3.7725	1.0680	1.2545
0.50	3.7306	3.5207	0.9080	1.0477
0.70	1.5024	1.3020	1.3400	1.4550
1.00	3.18226	2.9590	2.1200	2.2200

Table 2. Integral (\bar{D}) and differential (D) diffusion coefficients ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$) of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ -PBW-373 wheat system at 25° and 45°

Concn. mol dm^{-3}	25°		45°	
	\bar{D}	$D \times 10^4$	\bar{D}	D
0.01	1.6498	1.8106	2.8620	4.3063
0.03	1.8028	1.9513	1.4728	—
0.05	1.3243	1.4826	—	—
0.07	1.4573	1.6247	1.7047	1.9169
0.10	2.1984	2.9559	1.5518	1.2288
0.30	3.2638	3.3162	1.9829	1.2288
0.50	3.2728	3.4541	1.0414	1.5151
0.70	1.5024	1.3020	1.3400	1.4550
1.00	1.9630	2.9294	2.9920	3.0360

decrease with the increase in salt concentration. The results also indicate that the seed membrane acts as a very selective barrier towards solute transport and the role of hydration, changing viscosity and dielectric constant of the medium are other factors that may be considered responsible for the observed differences in D values of the two electrolytes.

Experimental

Wheat variety viz. PBW-373 was procured from the Department of Plant Breeding, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India and preserved in air tight containers. A.R. grade NaCl and CaCl₂.2H₂O were used and solutions prepared in conductivity water having a conductance of 10⁻⁶ mhos.

Diffusion cell :

A glass diffusion cell with a volume of 13 ml having the same specifications of the earlier design² was employed and single seed rather than bulk was taken. This reduction in cell volume from 23 to 13 ml was made simply to make the solution concentration easily measurable since conductance readings were taken to record the change in concentration with time during the diffusion experiment. The detailed procedure for filling the cell has been discussed earlier².

Determination of seed constant :

Seed constant (β_{seed}) is a characteristic of seed coat/membrane and its physiological nature and since these cannot be same for two different seeds of any two crop varieties it can be used for characterizing seeds. The basic equation relating the seed constant with average diffusion coefficient (\bar{D}), time t , and with the initial and final concentration differences between the seed and solution viz. ΔC_o and ΔC_f had been developed previously¹ and is given by :

$$\beta_{seed} = \frac{1}{Dt} \ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_f} \quad (3)$$

A modified procedure to estimate β_{seed} by the use of 0.01 M KCl has been proposed earlier² and, in this work the same was employed to determine the seed constant of the wheat variety. The values of β_{seed} were found to be 97×10^{-3} .

Diffusion runs with NaCl and CaCl₂.2H₂O :

Diffusion experiments using single seed of the wheat and NaCl and CaCl₂.2H₂O as the electrolytes (0.01–1.0 M) were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $45 \pm 0.1^\circ$. For every new experiment selection of the seed from the seed lot was so done that its weight is the same (upto third place of decimal) as the seed used for the determination of seed constant. Once β_{seed} is known, equation (3) can be rearranged to

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{\beta_{seed}} \ln \frac{\Delta C_o}{\Delta C_f} \quad (4)$$

which can now be employed for determination of \bar{D} , since time t , ΔC_o and ΔC_f are experimentally obtained from the diffusion experiment after the attainment of the steady-state conditions.

References

1. M. L. Sood, *J. Seed Sci. Technol.*, 1987, **15**, 255.
2. M. L. Sood and J. Singh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 635.
3. M. L. Sood and R. Dhir, *Seed Res.*, 2000, **28**, 22.
4. M. L. Sood and R. Dhir, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1998, **75**, 425.
5. M. L. Sood, *Seed Res.*, 1998, **26**, 109.
6. A. Passi, M.Sc. Thesis, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, 1999, p. 33.
7. R. H. Stokes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 763.